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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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METHODOLOGY FOR TEACHING MODAL VERBS IN ENGLISH LESSONS

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Abstract: The methodology of teaching modal verbs in English lessons is considered one of the most important and relevant issues. By mastering modal verbs, learners will be able to express their ideas clearly and concisely in both spoken and written communication. It is natural that certain difficulties and challenges may arise in the process of selecting and implementing appropriate teaching methodologies, since the meaning, usage, and grammatical functions of modal verbs are not easily acquired by students without sufficient prior knowledge. Therefore, the effectiveness of teaching modal verbs can be enhanced through the application of modern linguodidactic approaches, pedagogical technologies, and communicative methods.

Key words: modal verbs, English language, pedagogical technologies, grammar, communicative competencies, verbs, multimedia resources, online platforms.

Annotatsiya: Ingliz tili darslarida modal fe'llarni o'qitish metodikasi muhim va dolzarb masalalardan biri hisoblanadi. Til o'rganuvchilar modal fe'llarni o'zlashtirish orqali so'zlashuvda hamda yozma va og'zaki muloqotda fikrlarini aniq va lo'nda ifodalash imkoniyatiga ega bo'ladilar. Modal fe'llarni o'qitish metodikasini tanlash va uni amalga oshirish jarayonida ayrim murakkabliklar va muammolar yuzaga kelishi tabiiy. Chunki ushbu sohaga yetarlicha tayyorgarlikka ega bo'lmagan o'quvchi uchun modal fe'llarning ma'nosi, qo'llanilishi va grammatik vazifalarini o'zlashtirish qiyin kechadi. Shu sababli zamonaviy lingvodidaktik yondashuv, pedagogik texnologiyalar va kommunikativ uslublardan foydalanish orqali modal fe'llarni o'qitish samaradorligini oshirish mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: modal fe'llar, ingliz tili, pedagogik texnologiyalar, grammatika, kommunikativ kompetensiyalar, fe'llar, multimedia resurslari, onlayn platformalar.

Аннотация: Методика преподавания модальных глаголов на уроках английского языка является одной из важнейших и актуальных проблем. Освоив модальные глаголы, обучающиеся получают возможность ясно и лаконично выражать свои мысли как в устной, так и в письменной речи. Естественно, что при выборе методики обучения модальным глаголам и её реализации возникают определённые трудности и проблемы, поскольку значение, употребление и грамматические функции модальных глаголов нелегко усвоить студенту без достаточной подготовки. В связи с этим эффективность обучения модальным глаголам может быть повышена за счёт использования современных лингводидактических подходов, педагогических технологий и коммуникативных методов.

Ключевые слова: модальные глаголы, английский язык, педагогические технологии, грамматика, коммуникативные компетенции, глаголы, мультимедийные ресурсы, онлайн-платформы.

INTRODUCTION

English is currently one of the most widely studied and used languages worldwide. The language is an important tool not only in the field of international communication and business, but also in the fields of education, culture, and technology. By learning English, people not only expand their range of knowledge, but also have the opportunity to communicate effectively with other peoples. In addition, proficiency in this language plays an important role in the professional development of a person and the acquisition of new opportunities. The grammar, vocabulary, and pronunciation of the English language are characterized by their own unique rules, so it is necessary to study it in depth and systematically. In particular, the ability to express oneself quickly and clearly is important in the modern world. For this reason, the process of learning the English language not only consists of memorizing words or rules, but also includes many aspects such as understanding the culture of communication, listening and comprehension, and correctly expressing one's own opinion. This introductory part deals with the importance of the English language, the main goals in learning, and important aspects of

the learning process. It also focuses on the difficulties encountered in learning English and ways to overcome them, helping students to gain motivation in learning as well as to ensure effective learning. Since English has a place in all aspects of modern life, its mastery is considered important and necessary for everyone.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The study of English grammar has long been a central topic in Uzbek and Russian linguistics. Buranov emphasized the structural and functional features of English grammar, highlighting the importance of modal verbs in forming logical and meaningful sentences. Later, Hoshimov and Buranov expanded on this by presenting a normative course of English grammar, stressing the pedagogical need to explain modal verbs not only through grammatical rules but also by connecting them with communicative functions. These works demonstrate the foundational role of grammar in language teaching and provide teachers with a framework for systematically introducing modal verbs.

Further contributions were made by Osmanov and Ashurov, who analyzed the theoretical grammar of English with special attention to the semantic functions of modal verbs. Their research shows that modal verbs carry not only grammatical meaning but also pragmatic and stylistic functions that shape communication. Gapparov and Kasimova also stressed that teaching grammar, including modal verbs, should integrate theoretical explanation with practical exercises, ensuring that learners can apply rules in real communicative situations.

In a broader linguistic and pragmatic perspective, Batiuta explored speech acts in official documents, illustrating how modal verbs play a role in expressing obligation and necessity. Ergashova and Dexqonboeva examined forms of polite address in communication, which also relate to modal verb usage in maintaining speech etiquette. Similarly, Malyuga and Formanovskaya investigated speech etiquette in English and Russian, emphasizing that modal verbs function as markers of politeness, authority, and interpersonal relations. These studies confirm that modal verbs are not only grammatical elements but also key instruments in shaping communicative competence.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

When developing a methodology for teaching modal verbs in English lessons, teachers should initially pay special attention to the modern requirements of the language, the communicative approach, and the level and age of students' knowledge. First of all, the nature of modal verbs and their main semantic peculiarities, as well as the grammatical meaning expressed through them, are studied. The teaching of modal verbs uses context, their place in syntactic units, and their use as predicates. Modal verbs in English, notably words such as *must*, *can*, *may*, *should*, *will*, *might*, perform various functions. With these words, it is possible to express situations such as probability, permission, command, compulsion, possibility, and necessity. When teaching modal verbs in the course of the lesson, it is recommended to first abandon the traditional approach, because the peculiarities in this area are difficult to master in depth only by explaining grammatical rules and relying on memorization. Modern pedagogical approaches require the possibility of using modal verbs to be presented based on life contexts, in more practice-oriented assignments. The teacher develops students' thinking and elocution skills by organizing dialogues, role-playing games, discussions, and conversations during the teaching process ^[1].

With innovative methodologies, the process of teaching modal verbs can be organized in an interactive way. For example, through the extensive use of multimedia tools, electronic platforms, and online educational resources, the student's ability to work independently and practice knowledge is developed. After a brief description of the role and significance of modal verbs in the grammatical system of the English language, it is useful to create as many real-life situations as possible. This allows students to deeply and consciously assimilate new knowledge. In the development of methodological materials and in the planning of classes, a step-by-step teaching system has been observed in recent years. First, modal verbs and their basic forms are explained, then exercises are performed on their correct use in sentences, and afterwards the knowledge gained is consolidated in various practical tasks. In this case, it is recommended to expand the ability of students to independently compose a sentence or text, and to express an opinion both verbally and in writing. As a result, an understanding is formed not only of the grammar of modal verbs, but also of their semantic and stylistic features. After all, it is important not only to memorize the rule, but also to be able to use modal verbs correctly and purposefully in various communicative situations. With modal verbs, the language learner must be able to express his point of view, build a confident and strong sentence, and express notions such as probability, necessity, or permission ^[2].

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In today's English teaching practice, the effective use of modern information and communication technologies in teaching modal verbs leads to effective results. When teaching, it is recommended to combine traditional and innovative techniques, to use electronic textbooks, online trainings, video and audio materials, in addition to visual tools and close-to-real-life assignments. This increases students' interest and motivation in English, developing their ability to work independently and think creatively. Within the methodologies used, the communicative approach occupies a special place. This technique teaches the language learner to express opinions clearly and succinctly in real communicative situations, including ensuring the natural and appropriate use of modal verbs. It is important that practical exercises and assignments always reflect life situations, since it is through real-life contexts that students can freely, quickly, and correctly use modal verbs. This serves to develop oral and written speech culture. Another important aspect in methodological approaches is the establishment of differentiated education. Taking into account the individual characteristics of students and their level of knowledge and training in the lessons, it is advisable to choose the methods and styles that suit each student. In addition to working independently, students are also taught to work in groups and pairs. In this process, various nuances of modal verbs are studied in depth; learners demonstrate their knowledge and skills to each other, discuss together, and exchange ideas. Relying on linguodidactic sources, the importance of modal verbs in basic styles such as oratory, treatment, notification, questioning, and rejection in English should also always be in the spotlight. It is also important in the process of modern education to monitor appropriately developed diagnostic cards, and the knowledge and skill levels of each student. Using various games, quizzes, and creative assignments in lessons, students' knowledge is regularly monitored and the stages of mastering modal verbs are improved. In addition, it is also important to learn modal verbs through integrative approaches in connection with other grammatical subjects. For example, it is necessary to pay attention to separate exercises on the tense and conjugated forms of modal verbs, their ontological properties, and their use with synonymous modal constructions. This method helps to combine the teaching process into one whole system, and to carefully formulate the basics of a foreign language for the student. This approach helps the student transition from being dependent on the teacher to working independently and develops self-learning skills. It is also intended to address the lack of knowledge about cultural agreement and language in modern methodology, with a special emphasis on the specifics of modal verbs in communication. Modal verbs are widely used in English, specifically in business, formal, and informal communication. In the course of the lesson, it is necessary to clarify these differences and explain the specific expression of modal verbs corresponding to each situation ^[3].

Improving the methodology of teaching modal verbs in English lessons meets the requirements of modern education. The methodological process requires constant research, the combination of innovative and traditional approaches, individual approaches to students, communicative and practical assignments, and qualitative use of information and communication technologies. It is important that students are able to show activity and independence in everyday life, profoundly and thoroughly mastering not only the grammar of modal verbs, but also their real communicative function. The organization of interactive, practical, and creative activities, teaching them to think independently and critically, and to freely express their opinions is one of the most important tasks. This is achieved by using colorful methodological approaches so that students can effectively master modal verbs. To achieve this goal in modern educational institutions, it is necessary that teachers always master new methods and technologies anew, regularly learn the necessary pedagogical methods and approaches to increase students' motivation to learn the language, and try to conduct lessons more interestingly and efficiently ^[4].

It is natural for students to experience a number of difficulties in learning modal verbs. First of all, the grammatical features of modal verbs differ from traditional verbs in that they are not constant in their form and are usually used in the form of the main verb, that is, without proper suffixes. This situation makes it difficult for students to remember the rules and apply them correctly in practice. In addition, modal verbs have multifaceted meanings that can be interpreted differently in different contexts. For example, one modal verb may be used at some point to give permission, express a probability, or indicate an obligation. This makes it difficult for students to distinguish between different aspects and apply them in a suitable position. Since the rules of occurrence and application of modal verbs differ from other grammatical laws of the English language, students sometimes perceive them as ambiguous or confusing. Therefore, it takes a lot of practice to understand the role of modal verbs in sentence construction, the difference between literal translations, as well as the constructions inherent in them in a conscious way. Another difficulty is related to the different stylistic shades expressed using these verbs and how speech changes in different situations. The correct choice and use of modal verbs in formal and informal communication, and students' awareness of tone and intention, often lead to additional challenges. The specificity of modal verbs is due to the fact that they do not function as independent verbs. Sentences

formed with them mainly use the basic form of another verb, which creates confusion for learners about verb tenses and the opposition of mostly auxiliary verbs. Also, some learners try to adjust the translation of modal verbs to their native language, but this method often leads to incorrect application and logical errors. This creates a barrier to free and natural English speech. The teacher's approach also plays an important role. If modal verbs are taught only in the form of rules and on the basis of memorization, students cannot put them into practice because of a lack of real communicative contexts. For this reason, students have increased difficulties in understanding this topic in depth. As a result, more contextual, communicative, and interactive approaches should be used in teaching to overcome these problems. It is important for students to create opportunities to fully acquire and practice the lexical-semantic properties of modal verbs, as well as to identify and overcome individual difficulties through a personal approach ^[5].

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

As a conclusion, it can be said that all the work carried out on the methodology for teaching modal verbs in English lessons serves to develop the speech competence of students, to form them as independent and active-thinking individuals, and to cultivate competitive specialists in accordance with the requirements of modern society. At the same time, the improvement of the methodological approach, the continuous connection of practical tasks with real life, and the effective application of pedagogical techniques and innovative tools have their place for each English teacher and student, and are important instruments in the consistent improvement of the quality of language teaching.

The methodology for teaching modal verbs in English lessons should be organized in effective and logical stages. First of all, it is necessary to clearly explain to learners the theoretical foundations of modal verbs and their general scope of application. At this stage, interpreting the lesson material using simple and clear examples will increase students' interest in the topic and strengthen understanding. It is also necessary to indicate the specific functions of modal verbs, such as expressing possibility, probability, permission, and obligation. In the teaching process, it is useful to apply interactive methods. Through interviews, role-playing games, and assignments, students have the opportunity to practice modal verbs. For example, students express their thoughts using verbs such as can, must, should in various situations. This will not only help them memorize the rules of grammar, but also increase their confidence in using the language.

It is also recommended to include a large amount of listening and reading materials in lessons. For example, it is effective to show how modal verbs are used in context through short stories, dialogues, or audio-visual materials. Such an approach develops not only students' theoretical knowledge, but also their communication skills in real life. It is also necessary to focus on independent work as part of the lesson. Modal verbs can be reinforced by giving students exercises, tests, and written assignments. This is important in identifying and correcting their errors. The teacher must constantly maintain an individual approach, giving tasks corresponding to the level of each student. Some students may need more hands-on training, while others may need theoretical explanations. This makes the learning process effective and engaging.

The use of modern technology in teaching modal verbs is also considered useful. With the help of online platforms, interactive applications, and mobile applications, students can independently perform many exercises and check their answers. This gives them an impetus for self-assessment and active learning. In general, the methodology for teaching modal verbs should be reinforced by step-by-step practical exercises and constant communication. This not only increases the language skills of students, but also prepares them to speak English. Thus, when teaching the subject of modal verbs, it is important to take into account interactivity, adaptation to real situations, and an individual approach.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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